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Exploring processor micro-architectures optimised for BLAS3 micro-kernels

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Abstract. Dense matrix-matrix operations are relevant for a broad range of numerical applications, e.g. for implementing deep neural networks. Past research has led to a good understanding of how these operations can be mapped in a generic manner on typical processor architectures with multiple cache levels such that near-optimal performance can be reached. However, while commonly used micro-architectures are typically suitable for such operations, their architectural parameters need to be suitably tuned. The performance of highly optimised implementations of these operations relies on micro-kernels that are often handwritten. Given the increased variety of instruction set architectures and SIMD instruction extensions, this becomes challenging. In this paper, we present and implement a methodology for an exhaustive exploration of a processor core micro-architecture design space based on gem5 simulations. Furthermore, we present a tool for generating efficiently vectorised code leveraging Arm’s SVE and RISC-V’s RVV instructions. It enables automatization of the generation of micro-kernels and, therefore, the generation of a large range of such kernels. The results provide insights both, to micro-architecture architects as well as micro-kernel developers. The assembler generator is open-sourced and the simulation data is available as supplementary material.

Keywords: Processor micro-architectures, dense matrix-matrix multiplication, SIMD/vector instructions, assembly generator, gem5 simulations

1 Introduction

Dense matrix-matrix operations are relevant for a broad range of numerical applications, most notably applications in the area of machine learning. Various such operations have in the late 70s been implemented in a numerical library called Basic Linear Algebra Subprograms (BLAS)³, where these operations have been classified as “level 3”. This library became quickly very popular and the

³ <https://www.netlib.org/blas/>

library’s API has become a de facto standard, which is used for various high-performance implementations. Some of the most popular open-source implementations for general-purpose processors are OpenBLAS [20] and BLIS [19]. They have their roots in GotoBLAS, which is based on a systematic analysis of how matrix-matrix operations can be mapped in a generic manner on typical processor architectures with multiple cache levels such that near-optimal performance can be reached [7]. This work has later been refined using analytical performance models (see, e.g., [11]) that allowed fixing of various implementation parameters based on computer architectural parameters. In the following, we focus on a specific subset of BLAS level 3 routines, namely the so-called gemm routines that implement the operation $C \leftarrow \alpha \cdot A \cdot B + \beta \cdot C$ (and variants). A , B , and C are matrices while α and β are scalar numbers.

Today’s optimised implementations of the gemm routines are all based on a set of nested loops with an innermost loop body containing a small matrix-matrix multiplication, the so-called micro-kernel. The organisation of the outer loops depend mainly on the memory hierarchy, e.g. number of cache levels or cache sizes. Assuming a suitable performance of the L1 data cache, the performance of the micro-kernels depends only on the features of the micro-architecture. These kernels are typically manually optimised using assembler instructions. The main research question of this paper is, how key parameters of the micro-architecture and the micro-kernel are related to each other.

Unlike most research on BLAS level 3 routines, which focuses on one or few micro-architectures based on available processor products, we rather consider a larger design space leveraging the gem5 simulator [3,12]. Furthermore, note that many different micro-kernel implementations are considered, i.e. the benchmark is not fixed like in many other design space explorations. We aim to provide insights relevant to both, developers of processor micro-architectures and developers targeting micro-kernels.

For our approach, we developed an assembler-generating tool for creating micro-kernels supporting different Instruction Set Architectures (ISAs) including Arm-v8 and RISCV-V plus relevant SIMD extensions, namely Scalable Vector Extension (SVE) [18] and RISC-V ”V” Vector Extension (RVV) [2], respectively. For our simulations, we use a parametric simulation model that is aligned with the latest generation of Arm server-class cores, namely Neoverse [17]. Arm-based processor architectures have recently become increasingly widely used to realise high-end HPC systems and large-scale Cloud infrastructures with the introduction of Fujitsu’s A64FX and several generations of Kunpeng and Graviton processors from HiSilicon and AWS, respectively. We also started to look at RISC-V-based architectures because of the emerging efforts towards realising high-end processors (and accelerators supporting vector instruction) based on this ISA. The exploration is limited to the case of double-precision floating-point numbers (i.e. dgemm) but the methodology is easily extendable to single-precision numbers (sgemm) or (with some additional efforts) to gemm routines with complex numbers (cgemm/zgemm).

This paper makes the following contributions:

1. A methodology for a systematic exploration of the design space of micro-architectures of processor cores for BLAS level 3 micro-kernels with a focus on processors based on the Arm architecture using the gem5 simulator and an assembler generator.
2. The tool for creating micro-kernels supports (among others) Arm SVE or RISV-V RVV instructions and is available open-source.
3. gem5 configuration files and simulation results as supplementary material for further analysis and reproducibility of results.
4. A comparison of performance results obtained from the model and selected hardware architectures.
5. A comparison of kernels for Arm SVE and RISC-V RVV.

After providing some background and references to related work in section 2, we describe our methodology in detail in section 3. Results obtained both, from our simulation model as well as existing hardware are presented and discussed in section 4. Finally, a summary and an outlook are provided in section 5.

2 Background and related work

It has early been recognised (see, e.g., [7]) that generic blocking and packing steps allow implementation of BLAS level 3 routines such that the data can be efficiently mapped to different levels of the memory hierarchy. This approach enabled the realisation of highly efficient libraries that have been optimised for various processor architectures based on a range of different ISAs (and corresponding extensions with SIMD instructions). In the innermost loop, a micro-kernel implements the operation $c \leftarrow c + \tilde{a} \cdot b$, where \tilde{a} , b , and c are matrices of size $n_r \times k_c$, $k_c \times m_r$, and $n_r \times m_r$, respectively. m_r and n_r define the register block size and k_c is one of the cache block sizes. (Note that we use the syntax of BLIS [19].) These matrices are small enough such that all their elements fit into the register file and L1 data cache.

For sufficiently large matrices A , B , and C this approach allows reaching good performance on typical processor architectures independent of the matrix size. Note, however, that this does not apply to matrices that are in one or both dimensions small. In these cases, matrix sizes can often not be ignored any more. To address this problem, the use of just-in-time (JIT) compilation technologies was introduced with LIBXSMM [9]. Alaejos et al. [1] took a different approach by providing micro-kernels implemented using intrinsics. In the following, we assume that the micro-kernels are used within sufficiently large loops and use an assembly generator as it provides faster code for different architectures.

Due to the relevance of numerical kernels like the gemm routines, these are used for the co-design of hardware architectures (see, e.g., [13,8]). This approach is, in particular, used for customised architectures. In this work, we assume commodity processor core architectures with a focus on Arm-based and an outlook towards RISC-V-based architectures.

SVE is a recently introduced extension of the Arm-v8 ISA [18]. Unlike many other types of SIMD instructions, SVE is vector-length agnostic, i.e. the width

of the SIMD instruction operands is not fixed. It could be any integer multiple of 128 bit up to 2048 bit. Note that while being able to generate binary programs that can adapt to hardware with different SIMD operand widths improves portability, it does not guarantee performance portability.

For RISC-V an extension has been introduced for vector instructions, which is called RVV [2]. It is also vector-length agnostic, but unlike SVE it allows single instructions to process a group of SIMD registers. In this way, a single instruction could process up to 524,288 bit. In this work, we do not consider grouping, i.e. we assume a vector register group multiplier setting of $LMUL=1$. Some preliminary performance results for RVV can be found in [16].

Simulations beyond the electronic circuit level have become very useful tools for processor core co-design as they enable fast exploration of design spaces for reasonably large numerical kernels. Simulators like gem5 [3,12] implement cycle-level models that allow for reaching good accuracy. (For a recent comparison of different simulators used for processor co-design, see [21].) It is, however, important to be aware of simulators being models that are only valid within a certain scope. This is also called the pragmatic property of models, emphasizing that they are created for a given purpose. (See [5] for a discussion of this and other model properties in the context of gem5 simulator-based models.)

Using assembler generators for generating highly optimised implementations of numerical kernels is a common approach. There are various trade-off decisions to be made concerning the number of supported numerical kernels, portability, level of control on code generation etc. Based on an evaluation of different solutions we concluded that implementing our own, highly specialised solution is the best choice. One reason was the lack of control of the generated assembler. For instance, TVM [6] relies on LLVM for producing code for CPUs. Another reason was the missing support for our target platforms. Here an example is EXO [10] with support for RISC-V RVV but not Arm SVE.

3 Methodology

In this section, we describe our methodology by first describing our modelling approach as well as our approach for design space exploration. Finally, we document how the large number of optimised kernels for the gemm routines have been constructed using an assembler code generation tool.

3.1 Processor core modelling

Our approach to modelling as well as the starting point for the model used for this work has been described in earlier work [5]. There we used AWS' Graviton 2 processor as model origin, a state-of-the-art server-class processor based on modern Arm Neoverse N1 cores [18]. Note that this processor does not support SVE, but from the simulations we found results for NEON SIMD ISA and 128 bit SVE to be rather similar. It is important to stress that, this choice was not made with the intention of delivering a highly accurate model for this specific

Fig. 1. Overview of the gem5 model’s micro-architecture.

processor architecture. The strategy of identifying existing hardware as model origin aims to create an initial model with mapping properties that match a realistic hardware architecture. This is not trivial to achieve as a gem5-based processor core model does not have easily identifiable truncation properties. Several architectural components are either missing or modelled in a simplified manner.

To facilitate design space exploration, we add to our initial model amplification and distortion properties. This means that we allow for features to be added, e.g. support for additional instructions like Arm’s new SIMD instructions SVE, or changes of properties with respect to the origin, e.g. changing the number of units for executing SIMD instructions. However, model amplifications and distortions have been done such that we stayed in a region of the design space where we could reasonably assume that a hardware architecture could be designed that maps well on this amplified and/or distorted model. For this, we took architectural choices into account for products that are at this moment available on the market. One example is the SIMD operand width, where currently no processors support an SVE operand width of more than 512 bit although the ISA would allow for up to 2048 bit. To explore the impact of larger operands, we allowed for one step beyond current products, namely 1024 bit.

In the earlier work, we introduced the following classification of model parameters: configuration parameters, tuned parameters and variable parameters. Configuration and tuned parameters are chosen to improve mapping between the origin and the model. The configuration parameters are chosen based on the technical specifications of the origin, e.g. size of caches. The tuned parameters are fixed such that observables like the execution time of a benchmark, which is run both on the origin and model, are similar. Variable parameters can be used for systematic distortion of the model, i.e. for design space exploration.

In Fig. 1, we provide an overview of the main components of our model, which has been derived from the O3CPU model available in gem5 (see [4] for further details). The most relevant configuration parameters are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Configuration and tuned model parameters.

Parameter	Value
Number of cores	1
L1D and L1I capacity	64 kiByte
Number of ports for loading/storing data from/to L1D	2
L1D access latency	4 cycle

Table 2. Exploratory model parameters.

Parameter	Symbol	Value range
Number of SIMD units	N_{SIMD}	1, 2, 4
SIMD operand width	w_{SIMD}	128, 256, 512, 1024 bit
SIMD FMA latency	$\lambda_{\text{SIMD,FMA}}$	4, 6, 10 cycle
Number of physical vector registers	$N_{\text{R,phy,v}}$	48-256 in steps of 2
Size of the re-order buffer (ROB)	N_{ROB}	8-256 in steps of 2
Number of reservation stations	N_{reserv}	8-120 in steps of 2

Although our approach foresees a single model origin only, we performed a comparison between other existing hardware and appropriately amplified and distorted versions of our model. We considered the following three processor architectures: HiSilicon Kunpeng 920, Fujitsu A64FX, and AWS Graviton 3. These three architectures differ significantly in terms of the architectural parameters, including SIMD operand width, number of SIMD pipelines, and SIMD floating-point instruction execution latency.

3.2 Relevant design space region

We start the design space exploration as follows:

1. Define the *design space* by selecting a suitable set of variable parameters as well as their value range.
2. Determine within this space a *relevant region* by identifying all points in this design space for which gemm micro-kernels can be constructed that do achieve good floating-point efficiency.

We define the floating-point operation efficiency as $\epsilon_{\text{fp}} = b_{\text{fp}}/B_{\text{fp}}$, where b_{fp} and B_{fp} are the obtained and theoretical maximum throughput of floating-point operations. We mark micro-kernels as “good” if they reach a floating-point operation efficiency $\epsilon_{\text{fp}} \geq \epsilon_{\text{fp,good}} = 95\%$.

The micro-kernels depend on the following implementation parameters: m_r , n_r , and k_c . The maximum values of m_r and n_r are limited by the number of available architected registers, which are defined by the ISA. In the following, we will define n_r in terms of the number of elements (here: doubles) and m_r in units of SIMD vectors. The value of k_c depends on the capacity of the L1 data cache, which we kept fixed in this paper as the memory hierarchy is beyond the scope of this paper. For larger k_c the costs for setting up the loop over k reduce relative to the costs for executing the loop resulting in higher performance.

To make the search for a relevant region manageable, the dimensionality of the design space needs to be kept sufficiently small. Here we apply different strategies. Firstly, we restrict ourselves to mainstream commodity processor core architectures supporting the Arm ISA including the SVE extensions. We foresee a SIMD instruction throughput of one instruction per cycle and SIMD unit.⁴ Furthermore, we assume the width of the ports to the L1 data cache to be equal to the SIMD operand width. Secondly, we exclude architectural parameters from the set of variable parameters that are either not relevant in the given context (e.g. the latency of floating-point add instructions) or that are not expected to provide relevant insights. An example of the latter is the latency of integer instructions, which is typically very similar for different processor products. Furthermore, we choose the latency of SIMD Floating-Point Multiply (FMUL) instructions equal to the one for SIMD Floating-Point Multiply-Add (FMA) instructions. This is justified by the observation that on typical hardware architectures, the latency of FMUL is usually the same or slightly smaller compared to FMA. Furthermore, in the micro-kernels, FMA instructions dominate. Finally, we introduce a distinction between two types of variable parameters, namely exploratory and determined parameters. The former are used for design space exploration, while the latter are fixed to sufficiently large values such that they do not impact performance. The values can be determined from suitable observables (see subsection 3.3). Examples are the rates at which instructions are fetched from the L1 instruction cache (B_{fetch}), issued to the functional units (B_{issue}), and retired from the functional units (B_{retire}).

The exploratory parameters are listed in Table 2. We choose to focus on parameters related to the SIMD instructions as they strongly impact the theoretical peak throughput of floating-point operations. The choice for the SIMD operand width (w_{SIMD}) followed market observations with the A64FX processor providing the largest width of 512 bit. Similarly, we observed the execution latency for SIMD FMA instructions ($\lambda_{\text{SIMD,FMA}}$) being in the range of 4 to 10 cycles. The chosen range for the number of execution pipelines, N_{SIMD} , is inspired by the observation that the HiSilicon Kunpeng 920 processor offers a single execution unit for double-precision NEON instructions, while the upcoming NVIDIA GRACE processor provides 4 execution units for 128 bit SVE instructions.

Some of the exploratory parameters are expected not to be independent of each other, namely the number of reservation stations (N_{reserv}) (in gem5: Instruction Queue size), size of the ROB (N_{ROB}), and number of physical vector registers ($N_{\text{R,phy,v}}$). Simulations allow us to explore such dependencies. For this purpose, we performed simulations where we kept within the design space all exploratory parameters fixed except for $N_{\text{R,phy,v}}$, N_{ROB} , and N_{reserv} using a fixed micro-kernel. We then selected different lower-efficiency threshold subsets of results for which $\epsilon_{\text{fp}} \geq \epsilon_{\text{fp,thres}}$. For each of these subsets, we performed a Pareto front analysis. In case of strong dependency between these variables, we

⁴ In case of architectures like the NEC SX-Aurora TSUBASA processor or the upcoming Vitruvius+ core [14], which supports RISC-V RVV, a vector instruction requires multiple cycles to feed operands into an execution unit.

expect the Pareto front to reduce to a single point. Note, that for sufficiently large values of N_{reserv} , N_{ROB} , and $N_{\text{R,phy,v}}$ the performance will become independent of these parameters.

3.3 Observables

From the simulations, we determine a set of observables that are listed in Table 3. For some observables, we had to extend the gem5 simulator.

For each point in the relevant region of the design space, we determined the number of “good kernels” (N_{good}), i.e. kernels with efficiency $\epsilon_{\text{fp}} > \epsilon_{\text{fp,good}}$, as well as the maximum achieved efficiency ($\epsilon_{\text{fp,max}}$). One would expect a larger value of N_{good} to be beneficial. Firstly, different micro-kernels may feature a different performance of the full gemm routines depending on the overall problem size. Secondly, more micro-kernels being available results typically in more choices for how to optimise depending parameters.

The other observables have been collected on a per design point and kernel basis. Based on the number of cycles required for executing the micro-kernel (Δt), the number of floating-point operations (N_{flop}), and the number of data, which is being loaded from and stored in the L1 data cache (I_{ld} and I_{st}), we can compute the average throughput of floating-point operations as well as the average bandwidth for transferring data between the core and the L1 data cache, respectively. The maximum number of architected registers needed for a specific kernel ($n_{\text{R,arch,max}}$) can be determined from the code generation tool and does not require simulations. The latter is, however, required to obtain the maximum usage of the reservation stations ($n_{\text{reserv,max}}$), ROB entries ($n_{\text{ROB,max}}$), and physical vector registers ($n_{\text{R,phy,v,max}}$). Finally, we collected information on the average throughput of instructions (IPC) as well as the maximum instruction fetch and issue rates ($b_{\text{fetch,max}}$ and $b_{\text{issue,max}}$).

3.4 Micro-kernel code generation

Our tool for generating assembly code for the micro-kernels has been written in Python.⁵ It leverages the similarity of the different SIMD ISA, the limited number of instructions that are required to implement the micro-kernels, and the similarity between the different kernels. This allows for an abstraction of relevant instructions such that one can implement a micro-kernel by writing an almost generic function where the sequence of instructions is replaced by function calls. These functions create, depending on the chosen ISA, the corresponding assembly code. The tool also manages the allocation of registers.

The abstraction of instructions includes floating-point arithmetic instructions (e.g. FMA), different load and store instructions, and instructions related to masking. Currently, the following SIMD ISAs are supported: AVX (using either 128 or 256 bit), AVX512F, NEON/ASIMD, SVE, and RVV.

⁵ The assembler code generator is available at https://gitlab.jsc.fz-juelich.de/nassyri/fma_indep_bench/-/blob/main/GEMM.md.

Table 3. Observables.

Observable	Symbol
No. of “good” kernels	N_{good}
Max. efficiency	$\epsilon_{\text{fp,max}}$
No. of cycles per kernel	Δt
Number of floating-point operations	N_{flop}
Efficiency	ϵ_{fp}
Data loaded/stored per kernel [Byte]	$I_{\text{ld}} / I_{\text{st}}$
Max. no. of reservation stations	$n_{\text{reserv,max}}$
Max. no. of ROB entries	$n_{\text{ROB,max}}$
Max. no. of phys. vector registers	$n_{\text{R,phy,v,max}}$
Max. no. of arch. registers	$n_{\text{R,arch,max}}$
Average IPC	IPC
Max. instr. fetch/issue rate [instr./cycle]	$b_{\text{fetch,max}} / b_{\text{issue,max}}$

The tool requires as input a choice of the data type (currently double and single are supported), ISA, and the register block sizes m_r and n_r . n_r and m_r have to be provided in units of data elements and SIMD vectors, respectively. In the case of vector-length agnostics ISAs like SVE, the actual length will be determined at run-time. Furthermore, the tool supports different strategies for managing the data of \tilde{a} and b , which allows, e.g., steering the generation of pre-fetch instructions. Also supported is the early load of array elements (preload).

The functions for generating micro-kernels are not completely generic as some differences between the SIMD ISAs cannot be fully abstracted. For instance, only the Arm SIMD ISAs supports a FMA instruction where multiplication happens with an element of a vector where the index is defined at compile-time.

If not otherwise specified, we use for a given architectural design point the micro-kernel that provides the best performance.

4 Results

With the methodology described in the previous section, we can generate a large number of simulation results. In this section, we present analysis results. The gem5 configuration files, all simulation results, and all possible kernels are available as supplementary material [15].

We start our analysis using a very large number of reservation stations, ROB entries, and physical registers such that these resources never become fully used. We observe a very clear trend in terms of the number of good kernels when increasing the number of SIMD functional units and/or increasing the latency of these units (see Fig. 2). Comparing results for $(N_{\text{SIMD}}, w_{\text{SIMD}}, \lambda_{\text{SIMD,FMA}}) = (1, 256, 4)$ and $(4, 256, 4)$ we observe that N_{good} drops from 41 to 6 and $\epsilon_{\text{fp,max}}$ from 0.991 to 0.968. Extending the comparison to larger latency, i.e. $(4, 256, 10)$, we see N_{good} and $\epsilon_{\text{fp,max}}$ even drop to 0 and 0.641. If we instead increase the SIMD operand width and compare $(1, 128, 4)$ and $(1, 1024, 4)$ we find N_{good} to

Fig. 2. Number of kernels with good kernels N_{good} for different design parameters.

increase from 31 to 39 and $\epsilon_{\text{fp,max}}$ marginally increase from 0.987 to 0.988. In summary, N_{SIMD} and $\lambda_{\text{SIMD,FMA}}$ are correlated parameters with a high impact, while w_{SIMD} has only a low performance impact. From this, we conclude that the micro-kernels can be designed such that they can very well exploit SIMD parallelism with a very high parallel efficiency beyond the range that is currently realised in processor products. On the other hand, it turns out to be difficult to exploit instruction-level parallelism, which is due to lacking architectural registers. The latter issue becomes even more pronounced when increasing the latency of the functional units. This defines a clear boundary for the relevant region within the design space given the constraints of the ISA.

We can, however, also observe a potentially beneficial effect of choosing larger N_{SIMD} . For larger N_{SIMD} we find kernels with smaller n_r to perform best, while $1 \leq m_r \leq 3$ remains small in all cases. Recall that the parameters n_r are in units of elements while m_r is in units of SIMD vectors. Smaller micro-kernels provide more opportunities for achieving good performance for small overall matrices.

The average throughput of instructions (IPC) is barely affected by the SIMD operand width. This was expected as many model parameters related to data storage and transport, e.g. vector register size or L1 data cache ports width, are scaled with the SIMD operand width. Increasing the number of SIMD functional units leads also to higher pressure on the other functional units, e.g. due to the increased number of load and store instructions. For $N_{\text{SIMD}} = 1$ we measure for the fastest kernel an $\text{IPC} \simeq 1.5 - 2$. For $N_{\text{SIMD}} = 4$ this increases to $\text{IPC} \simeq 4 - 6$.

Next, we consider trends in terms of L1 data cache bandwidth $b_{\text{L1}}(w_{\text{SIMD}}) = (I_{\text{ld}} + I_{\text{st}})/\Delta t$ for the most efficient kernel and fixed $(N_{\text{SIMD}}, \lambda_{\text{SIMD,FMA}}) = (2, 4)$. We observe a linear increase by a factor ~ 3 with $b_{\text{L1}}(128) = 10.5 \text{ Byte/cycle}$ and $b_{\text{L1}}(512) = 31.7 \text{ Byte/cycle}$. Naively, one would have expected (for constant clock speed) b_{L1} to increase by a factor 4. However, the best-performing kernels at both design points differ significantly in terms of arithmetic intensity $\text{AI} = N_{\text{flop}}/(I_{\text{ld}} + I_{\text{st}})$. In the case of the wide SIMD operands, we observe larger AI. Overall, this results in a relative reduction of the pressure on the L1 data cache ports. This effect can also be studied by comparing the effective bandwidth to the L1 data for different micro-kernels at a fixed point in the design space. In Fig. 3 we plotted b_{L1} for all good micro-kernels and fixed $(N_{\text{SIMD}}, w_{\text{SIMD}}, \lambda_{\text{SIMD,FMA}}) = (2, 512, 4)$. The values differ by almost a factor 2 showing that it is possible to obtain good performance with less bandwidth.

In Table 4 we list the results from the Pareto analysis described in the previous section. We observe that for the selected values of $\epsilon_{\text{fp,thres}}$ the Pareto front is

Fig. 3. L1D bandwidth in units of Byte/cycle for different good micro-kernels and $(N_{\text{SIMD}}, w_{\text{SIMD}}, \lambda_{\text{SIMD,FMA}}) = (2, 256, 4)$.

Table 4. Pareto analysis ($m_r=2, n_r=4, \lambda_{\text{SIMD,FMA}}=4, w_{\text{SIMD}}=256, N_{\text{SIMD}}=2$)

$\epsilon_{\text{fp,thres}}$	$(N_{\text{reserv}}, N_{\text{ROB}}, N_{\text{R,phy,v}}, \epsilon_{\text{fp}})$
50.0 %	(14,20,68, 50.1 %), (10,22,64,50.0 %)
60.0 %	(16,24,70, 60.8 %), (12,26,72,60.8 %), (12,30,68,60.7 %), (16,26,68,60.4 %)
70.0 %	(16,32,74, 70.5 %), (16,36,72,70.5 %), (26,34,72,70.6 %), (26,30,80,70.5 %)
80.0 %	(18,36,78, 80.3 %), (18,46,76,80.3 %), (26,38,76, 80.2 %)
90.0 %	(24,44,86, 90.6 %), (24,50,82,91.3 %)
92.5 %	(44,62,108, 92.6 %), (38,76,110, 93.3 %), (38,72,112, 92.7 %)
94.0 %	(42,74,108, 94.0 %), (40,76,110, 94.0 %), (48,70,112, 94.1 %)

very narrow indicating a strong dependence between the considered exploratory parameters N_{reserv} , N_{ROB} , and $N_{\text{R,phy,v}}$. We observe $N_{\text{ROB}}/N_{\text{reserv}} \simeq 1.4 - 2.6$ and $N_{\text{R,phy,v}}/N_{\text{reserv}} \simeq 2.3 - 6.4$. N_{reserv} being smaller compared to the other parameters can (at least in parts) be explained by reservation stations being occupied for a short period of time. It is interesting to observe that the selected micro-kernel benefits from a large $N_{\text{R,phy,v}}$, which is much larger than the number of architected registers. In other words, the kernel significantly benefits from register renaming. The parameters N_{reserv} , N_{ROB} , and $N_{\text{R,phy,v}}$ could alternatively also be determined through the observables $n_{\text{reserv,max}}$, $n_{\text{ROB,max}}$, and $n_{\text{R,phy,v,max}}$. For the parameters shown in Table 4 this would result in $(N_{\text{reserv}}, N_{\text{ROB}}, N_{\text{R,phy,v}}, \epsilon_{\text{fp,max}}) = (52, 78, 120, 94.2\%)$. However, the increase of hardware resources would result in a relatively small performance gain.

4.1 Comparison between model and existing hardware

In Table 5 we compare the efficiency of selected micro-kernels on the A64FX, Kunpeng 920, and Graviton 3 processors with results obtained using gem5 simulations. Overall, we observe similar efficiencies on the gem5 model and real hardware for both high-performing and low-performing kernels with the only exception of the less efficient kernel on Graviton 3. We suspect that the latter is caused by the simulator reading all operands of an FMA instruction at once while the hardware allows the operand for the addition to be provided late.

Table 5. Comparison between hardware and gem5 model for select microkernels

Processor	$N_{\text{SIMD}}, w_{\text{SIMD}}, \lambda_{\text{SIMD}}, \text{FMA}$	m_r, n_r, k_c	$\epsilon_{\text{fp}}/\text{hardware}$	$\epsilon_{\text{fp}}/\text{gem5}$
A64FX	2, 512, 10	2, 10, 128	99.8 %	96.8 %
	2, 512, 10	2, 4, 256	44.4 %	40.0 %
Kunpeng 920	1, 128, 4	1, 4, 1024	99.9 %	95.7 %
	1, 128, 4	1, 2, 1024	40.0 %	49.7 %
Graviton3	2, 256, 4	2, 4, 512	99.8 %	94.0 %
	2, 256, 4	2, 2, 512	68.3 %	49.4 %

4.2 Comparison Arm SVE versus RISC-V RVV

In this subsection, we compare Arm and RISC-V based on the assembler generated by our assembler generator. Both RVV and SVE are vector-length agnostic ISAs. They share similar instructions, but there are some notable differences:

- SVE requires for loads or stores less instructions for computing addresses,
- RVV has separate float and vector registers, and
- RVV’s support of grouping vector registers (i.e., $\text{LMUL} > 1$).

Those differences have consequences for the generated code. Additional addressing instructions in case of RVV would require a higher throughput of instructions. Architectures chosen by some in-development RVV-capable processors (see, e.g., [14]) can compensate this disadvantage by foreseeing longer vectors such that a single RVV instruction fills multiple stages of the vector pipelines.

With our approach, n_r must be $n_r < (32 - 2m_r - 1)/m_r$, as at least one vector register is required to load data from the B matrix. However, we multiply a vector of values from the A matrix by just one value from the B matrix. Using vector registers, we broadcast the value into the vector register and then perform an element-wise multiplication. If we use RVV’s `vfmac.vf` instruction we can use a floating-point instead of a vector register, increasing the upper limit to $n_r < (32 - 2m_r)/m_r$, allowing for 4 more large micro-kernel sizes with $(m_r, n_r) = (1, 30), (2, 14), (4, 6), (8, 2)$. As a side-effect, the renaming pressure on vector registers is also reduced.

5 Conclusions and outlook

In this paper, we presented a systematic approach for exploring the design space of processor micro-architectures for co-design with BLAS level 3 gemm routines. We implemented the approach using the gem5 simulator focusing on Arm-based architectures as well as a tool for generating assembly code implementations of the necessary micro-kernels. While the original model was tuned for Graviton 2, we found good agreement between results for appropriately distorted and augmented models and different state-of-the-art Arm-based processors. This generates trust in this modelling approach, which allows the identification of regions in a high-dimensional design space where good performance can be achieved assuming a memory hierarchy provides the required data transport capabilities.

A remarkable result is that the micro-kernels can take larger benefits from wide SIMD operands rather than more SIMD pipelines. In the case of a small number of pipelines, long pipeline latencies can be tolerated. The ability of performing out-of-order execution of instructions is critical with $N_{\text{reserv}} \gtrsim 30$ to achieve $\epsilon_{\text{fp}} > 90\%$. This may be more important for RISC-V as the number of instructions is larger. The latter may be compensated using long vectors.

The simulation results are publicly available to facilitate further analysis and exploration of architectural trade-off decisions.

Our next step will be exploring the memory hierarchy aiming at a comparison with previous analytic results [11]. The results presented in this paper provide already minimal requirements for loading and storing data from and to the L1 data cache, respectively. In particular, for large SIMD operand width, the throughput of instructions can be strongly reduced, which reduces performance requirements with respect to the L1 instruction cache as well as the processor core front-end. Furthermore, we plan to investigate multi-core simulation models to assess on-chip network performance as well as external memory performance requirements. Given various efforts on RISC-V-based architectures, in particular, some including the support of RVV, makes it also interesting to push support of this ISA in gem5. This work shows that the gem5 simulator can be a good environment for developing highly efficient software.

Acknowledgements and artifact availability

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References

1. Alaejos, G., et al.: Micro-kernels for portable and efficient matrix multiplication in deep learning. *The Journal of Supercomputing* **79**(7), 8124–8147 (5 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-022-05003-3>
2. Amid, A., et al.: RISC-V "V" Vector Extension Version 1.0 (2021), <https://github.com/riscv/riscv-v-spec/releases/download/v1.0/riscv-v-spec-1.0.pdf>
3. Binkert, N., et al.: The gem5 Simulator. *SIGARCH Comput. Archit. News* **39**(2), 1–7 (8 2011). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2024716.2024718>

4. Brank, B.: Vector length agnostic SIMD parallelism on modern processor architectures with the focus on Arm's SVE. Ph.D. thesis, Bergische Universität Wuppertal (2023). <https://doi.org/10.25926/BUW/0-43>
5. Brank, B., Pleiter, D.: CPU Architecture Modelling and Co-design. In: Bhatele, A., Hammond, J., Baboulin, M., Kruse, C. (eds.) High Performance Computing (2023). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-32041-5_1
6. Chen, T., et al.: TVM: An Automated End-to-End Optimizing Compiler for Deep Learning. In: 13th USENIX OSDI Symposium. pp. 578–594 (10 2018), <https://www.usenix.org/conference/osdi18/presentation/chen>
7. Goto, K., Geijn, R.A.v.d.: Anatomy of High-Performance Matrix Multiplication. ACM Trans. Math. Softw. **34**(3) (may 2008). <https://doi.org/10.1145/1356052.1356053>
8. Haris, J., et al.: SECDA: Efficient Hardware/Software Co-Design of FPGA-based DNN Accelerators for Edge Inference. In: 2021 IEEE 33rd International Symposium on Computer Architecture and High Performance Computing (SBAC-PAD). pp. 33–43 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1109/SBAC-PAD53543.2021.00015>
9. Heinecke, A., et al.: LIBXSMM: Accelerating Small Matrix Multiplications by Runtime Code Generation. In: SC 2016. pp. 981–991 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1109/SC.2016.83>
10. Ikarashi, Y., et al.: Exocompilation for Productive Programming of Hardware Accelerators. In: PLDI 2022. p. 703–718. PLDI 2022, ACM, New York, NY, USA (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3519939.3523446>
11. Low, T.M., et al.: Analytical Modeling Is Enough for High-Performance BLIS. ACM Trans. Math. Softw. **43**(2) (8 2016). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2925987>
12. Lowe-Power, J., et al.: The gem5 Simulator: Version 20.0+ (2020). <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2007.03152>
13. Merchant, F., et al.: Accelerating BLAS on Custom Architecture through Algorithm-Architecture Co-design (2016). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1610.06385>
14. Minervini, F., et al.: Vitruvius+: An Area-Efficient RISC-V Decoupled Vector Coprocessor for High Performance Computing Applications. ACM Trans. Archit. Code Optim. **20**(2) (3 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3575861>
15. Nassyr, S., Pleiter, D.: Artifact of the paper: Exploring processor micro-architectures optimised for BLAS3 micro-kernels (June 2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11671717>
16. Nassyr, S., et al.: Programmatically Reaching the Roof: Automated BLIS Kernel Generator for SVE and RVV. In: RISC-V Summit Europe (2023)
17. Pellegrini, A., et al.: The Arm Neoverse N1 Platform: Building Blocks for the Next-Gen Cloud-to-Edge Infrastructure SoC. IEEE Micro **40**(2), 53–62 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1109/MM.2020.2972222>
18. Stephens, N., et al.: The ARM Scalable Vector Extension. IEEE Micro **37**(2), 26–39 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1109/MM.2017.35>
19. Van Zee, F.G., van de Geijn, R.A.: BLIS: A Framework for Rapidly Instantiating BLAS Functionality. ACM Trans. Math. Softw. **41**(3) (June 2015). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2764454>
20. Xianyi, Z., et al.: Model-driven Level 3 BLAS Performance Optimization on Loongson 3A Processor. In: IEEE 18th ICPADS Conference. pp. 684–691 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICPADS.2012.97>
21. Zaourar, L., et al.: Multilevel simulation-based co-design of next generation HPC microprocessors. In: 2021 International PMBS Workshop. pp. 18–29 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1109/PMBS54543.2021.00008>